

A PRELIMINARY CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE KUBA KAOLIN DEPOSIT, JOS PLATEAU (NORTH-CENTRAL NIGERA).

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ABSTRACT

A preliminary investigation of the kuba kaolin located within the southern part of the Rop Complex was carried out to determine its physical and chemical characteristics, origin and possible industrial applications.

Chemically, the Kaolin has low Fe_2O_3 wt.%, Na_2O wt.%, K_2O wt.%, SO_4^{2-} wt.%, HCO_3^{2-} wt.% and high SiO_2 wt.% contents. The particle size analysis indicates low impurity and a very high proportion of clay-sized materials. The plasticity index ranges from 10.6% to 12.6% which falls within the characteristic plasticity range for Kaolin (10-60%) and therefore falls into the class of plastic Kaolinites. They also have low drying and firing shrinkages while the loss on ignition is between 2-13% which falls within the theoretical value of 13.9% accepted for pure Kaolinites. The results obtained suggest that the kuba Kaolin is residual and is from a granitic parent. It will be suitable for use in the production of paper, paints and ceramics. Improvement in the processing of SiO_2 can make it possible for the clays to be used in the manufacture of cement and fertilizers.

KEYWORDS: Kaolin, Plasticity, residual, granitic, Rop Complex, industrial applications.

INTRODUCTION

Kaolin, like most of the kandite group of minerals, is either formed as a product of the chemical weathering of pre-existing granite rocks and feldspars (as well as feldspar related), especially in warm tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world or as a result of the hydrothermal alteration of granite. Residual or hydrothermally formed kaolin could be eroded, transported and deposited in a favourable environment to yield sedimentary kaolin (Emofurieta, *et al*, 1992).

Kaolin is used in the manufacture of refractories, ceramic wares, chemical, paint, paper, rubber and pharmaceutical industries among others. Most of the relevant industrial properties of the raw clay are dependent on the composition (mineralogical and chemical), particle size distribution as well as the grain shape. Kaolin therefore, is an important raw material for many industries although some industrial applications require the blending of the kaolin with other materials (like feldspar and quartz in the ceramic industry) so as to improve on some desired characteristics of the finished products (Emofurieta, *et al*, 1992).

This paper reports the results of preliminary studies carried on the chemical composition and some physical properties of the kaolin deposit in Kuba area Jos Plateau area, North Central Nigeria with a view to determining its origin and industrial application.

Location and Geology.

The Kuba area is located in the southern part of the Rop Complex. It is bounded by Longitudes $8^\circ 55' \text{ E}$ - $8^\circ 59' \text{ E}$ and Latitudes $9^\circ 28' \text{ N}$ - $9^\circ 24' \text{ N}$ to the North East of Kurra (sheet 189) in Jos Plateau. (Figure 1). It is a roughly triangular area of 360 km^2 of which 105 km^2 are underlain by the Younger Granite suites. The geological succession of the main types in the study area are shown in Table 1.

The Basement Complex rocks are the oldest rocks. They underlie the study area and include Granite-gneiss, Migmatite, and some Older Granite rock suites.

The Younger Granite rocks belong to the Rop Complex. They include biotite- microgranites, pyroxene, riebeckite, biotite and hornblende biotite granites. The Younger Granites appear as isolated and resistant masses and are Jurassic (141-192.5 m years) in age.

The volcanic rocks found in this area are the Older and Newer Basalts with the Older having undergone substantial degree of weathering. The newer basalts are thought to be late Tertiary in age¹⁰ and were believed to have erupted after the Plateau had achieved its present topography. The Older Basalts of the area are early Tertiary in age and have been lateritized in some areas. The lateritic capping generally protects the rocks from agents of erosion. The basalts outcrop at North – East of Gana Daji and North – East and South West of Maikatako (Figure 1.). The Older and newer basalts always occur in association.

Table 1 GEOLOGICAL SUCCESSION OF THE MAIN ROCK TYPES

GEOLOGICAL PERIOD	AGE (M.Y)	LITHOLOGY	ROCKTYPE/REMARKS
Quaternary-Tertiary	18-65	Alluvium/Laterite	Youngest Foromation
Lower Tertiary	45-65	Lateritized Older Basalts	Largely decomposed overlying alluvial deposits
Jurassic	141-192.5	Younger Granites	Granite Porphyry. Biotite Granites, Pyroxene Granites etc
Precambrian		Crystalline Basement	Fine to Medium grained biotite Granites, Migmatite, Quartz Diorite

(Adapted from Macleod, *et al*, 1971).

The alluvial deposits in the area have been grouped into three groups:

- i. Those in the draining systems
- ii. Deep leads beneath the Basalts
- iii. Deep leads beneath the fluvio volcanic series.

Table 2:Description of Samples collected for Analysis

Samples	Locations	Description of Samples
B48	A	Mottled type of Kaolin, bright white colour, iron stained
B48	C	Slightly weathered, fine- grained with slight staining pink kaolin.
B24	B	White, fine-grained and lineated type of clay.
B121-B124	E	White, fie-grained, non-lineated type of clay. High grade
B32	F	Slightly weathered and coarse-grained kaolin.

The primary source of the alluvials are from the Younger Granite of the Rop complex.

The laterites occur mainly in the western part of the mapped area and also in few other parts of the areas covering some outcrops. The vary in colour from light-brown (with quartz pebbles) to reddish brown that is highly ferruginized. The thickness of the laterite capping varies from 15 cm to 1.5m. The lateritic soil supports subsistence farming in the area especially where mining ponds provide water for irrigation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

Sampling

Twelve samples were collected from five vertical sections as described below. The sampling was done with the aid of a hammer, plastic, hand shovel. chisel and allot ladder. Storage of the samples was done in closed polythene bags. The samples that were collected from the field and subjected to various tests are presented in the Table 2.

Area A (Lat. 9°25'N and Long 9°57'E)

This occurs about 1 km from Maikako (Figure 1). There is an abandoned tin mining pit just after descending from the basaltic hill in the south east direction. The tailing brought out from this pit is kaolinized. The mining pit is about 8m deep with laterite capping and bouders of basalts occurring on top of the kaolin. (Figure 2a). The kaolin here is of poorer grade. Large phenocysts (crystal) of quartz and feldspar were observed and this indicates that the kaolin is of granitic origin. The kaolin samples collected were labeled as B48₂ and B48₃ and were observed to be of mottled type and white in colour with iron stains (Table 2,Figure 2a). The rock types that characterise this area are Migmatite, basalt and laterite (Figure 1).

Area B (Lat. 9°25 'N and Long. 9°56'E)

This area is around Kuba on the Barakin Ladi – Bokkos road (Figure 1). This area is plain except for the outcrop of migmatite which rises above the plain and it is lateritized. There are two abandoned mining pits in this area and both of them are about 7m deep and 50m wide. The tailings from these mining pits are kaolinized and left as hilly dumps around this area. The tailings have been hardened due to the cementing nature of kaolin that are present in the tailings.

Table 3: CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF KUBA KAOLIN DEPOSIT AND SOME REFERENCE MATERIALS.

	B48	B43	B24	B121-124	B34	A	B	C	D	E	F
SiO ₂	45.69	45.52	46.74	44.35	75.20	45.57	52.92	57.67	46.88	63.20	59.00
Al ₂ O ₃	36.28	35.02	35.00	34.51	14.98	38.45	9.42	24.00	37.65	25.61	26.66
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.63	3.80	3.43	2.26	0.64	0.75	3.65	3.23	0.88	1.52	1.81
MgO	0.12	0.04	0.08	-	1.01	0.05	0.08	0.30	0.13	0.05	0.07
CaO	0.11	0.11	0.06	-	0.84	-	1.91	0.70	0.03	0.10	0.66
Na ₂ O	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.07	0.02	-	0.03	0.20	0.21	0.29	0.75
K ₂ O	0.60	0.08	0.67	1.11	2.89	0.06	0.98	0.50	1.60	1.75	0.38
TiO ₂	0.73	1.00	0.78	1.20	0.38	0.01	1.18	-	0.09	0.22	0.52
P ₂ O ₅	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.02	-	-	0.03	0.02
MnO	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	-	-	-	-	0.01	0.004
H ₂ O+	-	-	-	-	-	10.19	10.50	12.45	8.00	10.10	10.10
HCO ₃	0.05	0.05	0.060	0.05	0.005	0.08	-	-	-	-	-
H ₂ O-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.70	-	3.50	13.05
SO ₄	0.04	0.11	0.66	0.05	0.07	-	-	-	-	-	2.13
LOI	13.00	11.88	12.30	12.16	2.00	-	-	3.35	-	-	-
TOTAL	98.29	98.92	99.24	98.77	98.22	84.98	89.41	97.10	99.92	100.79	100.48

Total Fe as Fe203.

- (a) Florida non-active kaolonite (Huber,1985), (b). Florida active kaolinite (Huber,1985), (c) Plastic Fire Clay St.Louis,M.O (Huber,1985), (d) China Clay GTY (Huber,1985), (e) Ibadan Residual Kaolin (average of 26 samples)(Emofurieta,1988), (f) Ozo-Nagogo Sedimentary Kaolin(average of 20 samples) (Emofurieta,1992)

TABLE 4:AVERAGE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND CHEMICAL SPECIFICATION OF SOME INDUSTRIAL CLAYS.

% Oxide	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
SiO ₂	49.88	47	47.90-45.30	45.78	44.90	44.90	45.90-45.80	45	67.50	51.00-70.00	38.67	46.07
Al ₂ O ₃	37.65	40.0	37.90-38.40	36.46	38.35	32.35	33.50-36.10	38.10	26.50	25.44	9.45	38.07
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.88	-	13.40-13.80	0.28	0.43	0.43	0.30-0.60	0.60	0.50-1.20	0.50-2.4	2.70	0.33
MgO	0.13	-	0.20-0.30	0.04	tr	tr	-	-	0.10-0.19	0.20-0.7	8.50	0.01
CaO	0.03	-	0.03-0.25	0.50	tr	tr	0.00-0.50	-	0.18-0.30	0.1-0.2	15.84	0.38
Na ₂ O	0.21	-	0.20-0.35	0.25	0.14	0.14	0.00-1.60	-	0.20-1.50	0.8-3.5	2.76	0.27
K ₂ O	1.60	-	0.40-0.10	0.25	0.28	0.28	0.00-1.60	-	1.1-3.10	-	2.76	0.27
H ₂ O+	12.43	13	-									
TiO ₂	0.09	-	13.80									
P ₂ O ₅			0.20									
MnO	-	-	0.30									
Total		-	0.03									
H ₂ O			0.25									
K ₂ O+			0.20									
Na ₂ O			0.35									
Fe ₂ O ₃			0.40									
+MgO			0.10									

- (1) Agricultural (Huber,1985), (2) Pharmaceutical (Todd,1973), (3) Paints (Paynes,1961), (4) Plastics (Frados,1965), (5) Cracking catalyst (Keller,1964), (6) Rubber, Paper, Textile (Huber,1985), (7) Ceramics (Singer and Sonja,1971), (8) Ceramics (Singer and Sonja,1971), (9) Refractory bricks (Parker,1967), (10) Brick clay (Nurray,1960), (12) Fertilizer (NAFCON,19

The samples of kaolin were collected in both mining pits and labelled as B24₁ and B24₂. Both of them are white, fine-grained and lineated type clay(Fig 2b,Table 2). The rock types that characterized this area are laterites which covers the largest part. Migmatite also outcrops in some places (Figure 1 and 2c).

Area C (Lat. 9°26'N and Long 9°56'E)

This area is around the Nigerian Mining Corporation (N.M.C) operational site. The kaolin exposure was observed at the old mining pit nearby. The mining pit provided a good cross-section of the lithology of the area, which is, kaolinized granite. Three horizons were exposed from where observations were made (Figure 2c, Table 2). These horizons are.

- (i) Laterite capping
- (ii) Kaolinized Granite
- (iii) Kaolinized Layer

The mining pit is about 8m deep and 60m wide. The samples of kaolin collected as B43₁, and B43₂ B43₃. (Figure 2c, Table 2). Kaolin is slightly weathered, fine – grained with slight pink- coloured staining. The rock types that characterize the area are riebeckite-biotite granite, biotite microgranite, laterite and alluvium (Figure 1 and 2c).

TABLE 5: RESULT OF SOME GEOTECHNICAL PROPERTIES OF THE KAOLIN IN THE STUDY AREA.

WET SEIVE(SEIVE ANALYSIS)				PLASTICITY %			Linear Volume Shrinkage		Linear Drying Shrinkage		Natural and Fired Colour	
SAMPLE No.	Wt % +200(in gms)	Wt % +200(in gms)	Wt % +200(in gms)	LIQUID LIMIT	PLASTIC LIMIT	PLASTICITY INDEX	110°C	1000°C	110°C	1000°C	NATURAL COLOUR	FIRE COLOUR AT 1000°C
B48	34.13	0.93	64.94	57.4	46.8	10.6	5.75	8.25	9.36	21.21	Very pink orange 10yr.8/2	Pinkish gray 5yr.8/1
B43	36.73	1.86	61.84	53.2	40.6	12.6	4.00	6.00	15.02	23.28	Pale yellowish orange 10 yr.8/6	Moderate orange pink 10yr 7/4
B24	11.57	2.64	85.79	61.3	50.6	10.7	3.50	6.00	16.60	23.21	Bluish white(5 B 9/1)	Bluish white(5 B 9/1)
B121-124	4.57	0.23	95.20	51.7	40.8	10.9	4.50	7.75	18.23	24.00	White (N 9)	Bluish white (5B 9/1)
B32	11.17	11.53	68.47	NIL	NIL	NIL	3.13	3.75	9.09	10.83	Yellowish grey 8yr/81	Pale Yellowish orange 10 YB/6

Area D (Lat. 9° 25'N and Long 9° 57'E)

This area is around Fanjol settlement, south-east of Ganan Daji. Alluvial deposits could be worked along the river and at the edge of the river, Kaolin deposit could be seen to be exposed at the surface. The depth from the ground level to the water surface is about 5m and kaolin was seen to be exposed from this depth (Figure 2d). The sample of kaolin collected was labeled as B20. The kaolin is white in colour with some traces of oxidized iron (Fig

2d, Table 2). The rock types characterizing the area are Migmatite, hornblende-biotite granite, laterite, and alluvium (Figure 1).

Area E (Lat. 9° 27'N; and Long. 9° 55'E)

The area is around the Major porter and Tudun Mazat villages northwest of the mapped area. At major porter villages, the granite was observed to be kaolinized. About 500m northwest of Major Porter village, the mining site of consolidated Tin Mining (CTM) is situated. The tin mining pit which is 60m deep exposed the kaolin. At the mining site, the profile observed are thick laterite capping, white kaolin red lineated kaolin and kaolin mixed with quartz (Figure 2e, Table 2). These are underlain by tin-bearing bedrock from where the tin is being mined which is intersected by another kaolin deposit (Figure 2e). The samples collected are labeled B12₁, B12₂ and B12₃. The major rock types which characterize this area are biotite microgranite, hornblende-biotite granite, laterite and small outcrops of basalt (Figure 1)

Area F (Lat. 9° 27'N; and Long. 9° 57'E)

This area is around Rafin Karfi, northeast of Gana Daji. The area comprises of rivers in which Loto mining of cassiterite is carried out. Weathering and erosion are intense here.

The river exposed the kaolin which is brightly white in colour with quartz pebbles and shows evidence of granitic origin. The kaolin sample collected was labelled as B32. (Table 2, figure 2). The major rock types that characterize this area are basalts, granites and a lot of pegmatitic veins that criss-cross each other.

Sample Analyses

The laboratory test carried out included chemical analysis, wet sieve analysis, Linear and drying shrinkage and plasticity test, firing colour and crushing strength.

The chemical analysis was determined by Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The geotechnical Index properties (physical) were generally carried out according to procedures specified by the British standard institution (BS1924; 1975) and the American society for Testing and Materials (ASTM 1928; 1979).

For the wet sieve analysis, about 100g of each sample collected from areas A, B, C, D, E and F were poured into water jars and mixed very well after which the water jars were left for 24 hours to allow the particles to settle according to their sizes. Sieving was then carried out using +200 mesh, +300 mesh (British standard). Particles that remained on a sieve were regarded as over-size of the sieve while those that passed through the apertures were under-size. The Tyler sieve set was used for sieving and the materials weight afterwards. Residue on the + 200 mesh (0.075-0.25mm) were regarded as sand particles, residues on the + 300 mesh (0.075-0.25mm) as silt particles and residues of the - 300 mesh (<0.075) as clay particles.

Plasticity is the property of the clay that allows cracking and is influenced by mineral composition, fineness of the grains, moisture content and presence of colloids. Plasticity is one of the most important properties of clay, as it affects the dry strength and shrinkage. Clay can also have their activity in terms of the plasticity characteristics altered by substitution of metallic ions of higher order as in the following substitution scale:

According to this scale, Ca will replace Na or Mg more easily than either Mg or Na will replace Ca. Plasticity was measured in terms of the plastic limit, which is the minimum water content at which the clay can be rolled into a thread 3mm diameter without breaking up, and also in terms of the liquid limit which is the minimum water content at which the clay will flow under its own weight. They are expressed as weight % of the clay dried at 110°C.

The plasticity index (PI) is the range of water content over which a soil is plastic. This is expressed mathematically as the difference between the plastic limit (PL) and liquid limit (LL) i.e.

$$\text{PI} = \text{LL} - \text{PL}$$

The above gives a good indication of probable behaviour of the clay under pressure. Linear shrinkage on the other hand is given by a reduction of the total clay mass on drying and firing. This property influences the permeability, hardness and strength of the finished product. For this test, the clay was molded into small bricks (at room temperature) and the length measured. These were then dried overnight at 110°C with the length being measured again. The difference between the length at 110°C and at room temperature are termed the linear shrinkage

values at 110°C the dry “ green “ bricks were then fired at 1000°C and lengths measured, the difference between the length at 1000°C and 110°C were termed the linear shrinkage values at 1000°C

Volume Shrinkage is given by the total change in volume of clay on drying and firing. This property also influences the hardness and strength of the finished product. They were molded into small bricks (at room temperature). As is done in linear shrinkage, the lengths, breaths and heights were measured for the volume, these were then dried overnight at 110°C. The differences in volume at 110°C and at room temperature were then termed the volume shrinkage value at 1000°C.

Natural and fired colours depend on the clay minerals and impurities present using the American standard colour chart. The natural colours of the dried samples were obtained as well as the colour changes produced when the bricks were fired to 1000°C for eight hours. Colour is an important determinant of several industrial uses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the chemical analysis are presented in Table 3 while those of the other geotechnical and some physical properties (sieve analysis, plasticity, linear and volume shrinkage, natural and fired colours) are given in Table 4.

Geochemistry

All the analysed clays in this study display similar geochemical characteristics except for sample B₃₂ that has high SiO₂ content (75.20%), Na₂O (0.02%), CaO (0.84%) and LOI (2%), low Al₂O₃ (14.98%) and Fe₂O₃ (4.603%Wt% - 47.35 Wt %). Silica and alumina vary from 45.52 - 45.69 wt.% and 34.51-36.28 wt. % respectively except for sample B₃₂ which has high SiO₂% (75.20%) and low Al₂O₃% (14.98%). This suggest that most of the clay are low to medium quality refractory varieties. The average range of SiO₂ (45-52%) and alumina (34.51- 36.28%) values are all within the range of values required by NAFCON (1985) and those of china clay (Emofurieta, 1988; Emofurieta, 1992;Huber,1985; Keller,1964)(Table 3).

The dominant contribution of Al₂O₃ in all the samples is kaolinite (Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)) hence the observed high contents of Al₂O₃ as well as SiO₂. These directly reflect the general purity of the clay deposits investigated. Other geochemical characteristics are low Fe₂O₃ (0.64% -1.63%), TiO₂ (0.38-1.00%), MgO (0.04- 1.01%), Na₂O (0.05 – 0.18%), and K₂O (0.60-2.89%) which fall within reasonable limits of those of the Florida active Kaolinite China clays (Adeyinka, et al;1968). K₂O is however higher in sample B₃₂. The low Fe₂O₃ content of the clays could be responsible for the good firing colour of the clays. These general characteristic of the clays suggests a similar origin which could be granitic. The chemical characteristics of the kuba kaolin shows that they are suitable for use in the paint,paper,pulp,rubber,plastic and agricultural industries(Huber,1985;Keller,1964; Nurray,1960;NAFCON,1985; .Parker,1967; Singer, *et al* 1971; Todd, (Ed) (1973) (Table 4).

Geotechnical Index and Physical Properties

The result of some of the geotechnical test and some of the physical properties are given in Table 4. On the sand silt: clay triangular diagram (Fig 3), all the samples fall within the clay fractions (<0.002mm). This shows that the kaolin contains high proportion of clay-sized materials and none of the samples fall into the sandy clay fractions which means the kaolin does not contain SiO₂ as grit. The high proportion of clay – sized materials in the kaolin makes it suitable for most industrial uses because grain size is an important specification in the paint, paper pulp, rubber, plastic and insecticide industries (Table 5).

The plasticity index ranges from 10.6 to 12.6 % for B₄₈, B₄₈- B₄₃, B₂₄, B₁₂₁₋₁₂₄. but the plasticity of B₃₂ could not be determined because the texture of the clay was found to be bad under test. The 10.6-12.6% range falls within the characteristic plasticity range for kaolinites (10-60%) (Figure 4). These clays are likely to exhibit low dry strength. A low plasticity index implies low moisture content range over which the clay will remain plastic.

The average liquid limit value is between 51.7-61.3%.This indicates that the clay can be worked through limited range of water content which can be of importance in the ceramic and paper industries where the behavior of the clay-water mixture is very important. The clays fall within the class of plastic kaolinites (Fig 5). Such clays are fine-grained and not well crystallized and so have high plasticity (Open University,1974). It also implies the presence of illite and or montmorillonite because kaolinite has low moisture absorptive capacity (Deer, et al,1966). This is important during the blending ,moulding and drying stages of the clay. If the material is very plastic, it may be prepared in the dry state, as well as in the wet state (Fakorede, 1977). The inability to determine the plasticity of sample B₃₂ as a result of its texture can be linked to the area which is still undergoing kaolinization.

The physical properties of the clays which were determined are: the natural and firing colours and the linear and drying shrinkage (Table 4). With respect to firing colours, all the samples exhibit slight colour changes when fired. Three firing groups of fire colour were obtained: White firing clays (B₂₄ and B₁₂₁₋₁₂₄) Pinkish gray/ orange colours (B₄₈- B₄₃) and yellowish orange (B₃₂). These firing colours are dependent on the amount of the oxides of iron and titanium. The white firing colours are probably due to low Fe content that would have changed the colour to red if present. Clays with iron oxide exceeding 2-3% usually give pinkish and / or reddish brown colour upon firing whereas those with lower percentages of iron oxides develop creamy, whitish or buff shades. In the ceramic, paper and paint industries, whitish firing colours are preferred in contrast to brownish / reddish colours which are preferred in the pottery and brick industries. The white firing clays (B₂₄ and B₁₂₋₁₂₄) can be used in the production of white- firing ceramics (porcelain, dinner ware sanitary ware etc), paper and paint. Refining those clays with whitish/ creamy colour to remove iron and titanium oxides will produce purer whitish colours acceptable for the production of paints and paper.

The linear and drying and firing shrinkages for all the samples are low and all of them exhibit similar drying behavior as deduced from the linear shrinkage graph (Figure 6a-e). The low shrinkage may be due to the fact that the clay was not heated up to the vitrification temperature. The fired samples are free from cracks, defects and warpage. The loss on ignition between 2-12.0% is within the theoretical value of 13.96% accepted for pure kaolinite (Adeyinka *et al*,1968). The dry strength of the product is a function of the shrinkage and loss on ignition. From the volume shrinkage graph, for samples B₄₈ and B₄₃(Figure 7 a-b), the firing shrinkage increases in the same way. This suggests the same physical properties for the two samples. Also from the volume shrinkage graph of samples B₂₄, B₁₂₁₋₁₂₄ and B₃₂ (Figure 7 c-e), it can be seen that the firing shrinkage also increase in the same way except sample B₃₂ which has a low firing shrinkage. This might be caused by its high Si₂O₂ content(Table 2).

CONCLUSIONS.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the study:

1. The Kaolin in the area has a high proportion of clay- sized particles with little sandy components. They fall within the class of plastic kaolinites and are fine- grained with fairly high plasticity.
2. The source rocks of the kaolin deposit is granite i.e. the kaolin is granitic in origin and residual in nature
3. The kaolin is of medium- grade based on the chemical analysis carried out. Hence the kaolin will be suitable for the production of ceramics, paint, tiles and refractories.

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Fig. 2A-E. Showing Profiles of the different sampling points.

Fig 3 Showing sieve Analysis Classification

Fig 4 Plasticity Index of clay minerals (Open University, 1973)

Fig 5. Identification Chart using Plastic Limit Index as Parameters

Fig 6 Liquid behaviour of the clay.

Figure 6A-E: Volume Shrinkage graph (Firing behavior) for Samples (A) B₄₈ (B) B₄₃, (C) B₂₄₁, (D) B₁₂₁-B₁₂₄ and (E) B₃₂

Figure 7A-E: Linear Shrinkage graph (Firing behavior) for Samples (A) B₄₈ (B) B₄₃, (C) B₂₄₁, (D) B₁₂₁-B₁₂₄ and (E) B₃₂

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